

Harnessing Water Bodies through Foxnut Cultivation : A Case Study of Madhubani District

Kumari Kshipra¹, Dr. Anuranjan²

¹Research Scholar, University department of Geography LNMU, Darbhanga (Bihar)

²Associate Professor, University Department of Geography LNMU, Darbhanga (Bihar)

Corresponding author- **Kumari Kshipra**

Email - kshiprasingh005@gmail.com

Abstract

Flood is the major problem of north Bihar, including Madhubani district. The loss of life, property and livelihood is very common. Madhubani is located in the foothill of Himalaya and the river's origin point is in Nepal which is the main cause of flood. It create very bad impact on the economy of region. So, we have to grow those crops which is not affected by flood. It is well-known that madhubani is enrich in water bodies. If we harness water bodies and prepare it for Foxnut cultivation then it will increase employment. There is favourable condition for the Foxnut farming and average productivity of the Foxnut is 1.5 tonn per hectare. So, the harnessing of water bodies and prepare it according to Foxnut will be a very good step in the flood-prone region of the Madhubani district. Those ponds which are not in use, we can also prepare it for Foxnut farming. But the absence of skilled workers, obsolete machinery, traditional method of farming, no more ideas of pond management, disease in Foxnut (Euryale Ferox), economic problem of farmers, lack of Makhana processing unit, government programmes did not give proper result etc. are the major problems. The research adopted both qualitative and quantitative method of data collection. Primary data is collected through focus group discussion, interview, questionnaire, schedule, probability sampling etc, where as secondary data is collected from the various magazines, research journal, govt. records, NGOs, books, ICAR and its related institutions, statistical water bodies and growing of foxnut (Euryale Ferox) in the context of flood prone region of the Madhubani district. It also discuss the various circumstances related with the Foxnut cultivation.

Keywords – Euryale Ferox, Harnessing, Water Bodies, Employment, Economy

Introduction:

Flood is a devastating natural disaster in North Bihar and especially common incidence in Madhubani. Every year loss of life, property and livelihood is very common. It not only affect the economy of the region rather it creates lot of problems for the people living in this region. The damage to the standing crops are very common in flood affected region. Therefore, such kind of crops which can easily survive in the flood-prone region should be promoted. Foxnut which is locally known as makhana is very suitable for farming in these region. Makhana is mainly produced in the Bengal, Bihar and Assam. Bihar has first position in the Makhana production in which maximum producing districts are Purnea, Supaul, Darbhanga, Madhubani, Katihar, Kishanganj, Araria and Sitamadhi.

Madhubani is an important district of the North Bihar, having suffer from the brunt of flood havoc almost every year. This is agriculture based region and the farmers of this region are badly affected from flood. Heavy destruction of crops from flood is very common at here . So, it is very important to grow those crops which can easily survive in the flood-prone region like Madhubani and the loss of farmers can also reduced from it. Foxnut (Euryale Ferox) or Makhana is the best option for the flood-prone region because it is an aquatic crop and there will be no risk of crop destruction of farmers during flood time because it can easily survive in flood region also. Harnessing of water bodies or Jalkars in the Foxnut cultivation

is very important. The district has leading position in the Foxnut production. The reason behind this is favourable condition for Foxnut cultivation in the Madhubani district. Average annual rainfall of 100-200cm, relative humidity of 60-80% and temperature of 25°-30°C is necessary for the Foxnut cultivation which is present in Madhubani district. Large no. of water bodies are also present in the region that's why it is known as 'Land of Ponds'. After Foxnut cultivation, raw Foxnut which is also known as Grey diamond can be processed in Makhana processing plant and ready product can easily supply in the market. The establishment of Makhana processing unit is very necessary for this but it is present in selected no. in the Madhubani district on the basis of private ownership. The government give subsidy on the establishment of processing plant but don't want to open directly. If the number of processing unit will increase then this region will be the hub of Makhana product.

Rationale of the Study:

Foxnut or Euryale Ferox is a favourable crop for the flood-prone district like Madhubani. While some farmers are showing interest in the foxnut cultivation because no only crop are ruined due to flood in some areas butalso it give more profit as compare to traditional crops. The present research is intended to find out the constraints present in the Foxnut cultivation, how to overcome it, its various scope in the near future. Flood is a recurrent feature of this region and standing crops are devastated usually every year. So, aquafarming or wetland

farming should be promoted. Foxnut and allied activities have good scope in this region.

Objective of the Research:

The present research work is intended to highlight the case study of Madhubani district by harnessing water bodies through Foxnut cultivation. There has been limited and sporadic studies of foxnut cultivation and its development, particularly in the Madhubani district. Hence, this research will give a step forward in this field to explore the potentials of this field in the Madhubani district. The main objective of the research is to find out the challenges which farmers are facing during the Foxnut cultivation, to trace out the major diseases which is harmful for the Foxnut crop and how to save crop from these diseases, potentials of Foxnut farming in the Madhubani district, can easily survive in the flood-prone region or not, climatic condition for the Foxnut cultivation, scope of Foxnut processing plant in the region, present condition of Government schemes and loan facilities for the Foxnut cultivators and those who want to establish Makhana processing unit, to find out factors behind the decreasing production of Foxnut in the Madhubani district in few decades and increasing in adjoining districts, evaluate the benefits of Foxnut cultivation as compare to traditional crop and the impact of polluted water bodies on the crops. These objectives of research will be very helpful to explore the possibilities of Foxnut in the near future and also

support in eradicating the drawbacks which comes during cultivation.

Study Area:

Madhubani is also known as the land of ponds, was carved out from the Darbhanga district in 1972. The region lies in the northern part of middle gangetic plain in the foothill of the Himalaya on latitude 26°34' N and longitude 86°7' E. Infact this region is very close to the tarai of Nepal. The total area of Madhubani district is 3,501 sq. km. The district is divided into 5 sub – divisions and 21 blocks. The population is 3, 570, 651 sq. km. The monsoon of here is influenced by the south – west monsoon (from June to September). The average annual rainfall of the Madhubani district is 1368 mm / 54.6 inch per year. The important rivers of this region are Koshi , Kamla Balan, Bhutahi Balan, Jeewach, Adhwara, Dhaus and Sugerwae which drained the region. Flood is the major problem of this region. About 70% population is directly or indirectly suffering from flood. Agriculture is the main source of livelihood of this region. About 12,000 ponds are located in the region and it will be very helpful for the economic development of the region. Ponds and wetlands are useful for the Foxnut farming. Benipatti, Andhrathadhi, Babubarhi, Jhanjharpur and Madhwapur are the major blocks of Madhubani district having large watery area and Foxnut production in these blocks are are also good where as Makhana processing planta are established in Benipatti, Andhrathadhi, Rajnagar and Pandaul.

Location Map of Study Area (Madhubani)

Hypothesis:

The study of this research needs formulation of some hypothesis. The important hypothesis are as follow:

1. This region has a rich tradition of foxnut production. The economic prosperity of the people in this region may be developed with the scientific development of Foxnut at large scale and it will be examined.
2. Foxnut and its allied activities have been overwhelmingly the main source of livelihood of a community (shahni family) since millennium and with the overall development it has strengthened the socio-economic conditions of this community.

Methodology:

The research is based on the data obtained from the both primary and secondary sources as well. Primary data is collected from the questionnaire, interview, focus group discussion, rapid rural appraisal (RRA) methods, purposive sampling and structured scheduled where as secondary data is collected from the government agencices, NABARD, BITCO, Agriculture offices, Block offices, NGOs, books, Journals, Magazines, ICAR affiliated research centers and institutions, Sastistical and Applied economics department.

Potentials in Field Of Foxnut Cultivation by Harnessing Water Resources:

Madhubani is enrich in water bodies and Foxnut (Euryale Ferox) farming is closely related to the tradition and culture of the Madhubani district but it needs to develop on large scale. Large acres of Wetlands, Barren lands, Unused ponds, chauras are available in the district which can easily prepare for Foxnut cultivation. Those areas where crops are ruined every year because of flood and farmers are facing heavy loss then Foxnut cultivation will be the best option for that region to decrease the crop destruction and increase the economy of the region. Madhubani is rich in the Foxnut production because the region have favourable condition for Foxnut cultivation. There is lack of processing unit in the region. If Makhana processing unit will be established then the region will become the manufacturing hub of Foxnut product which will be very helpful for the economy of region. Foxnut cultivation give more profit as compare to traditional crop farming and there is no risk of crop destruction because flood in the Foxnut farming. So, this crop will be the best option for the flood-affected region like Madhubani. Makhana or Foxnut has great nutritional and medicinal value. If we prepare Makhana products for commercial purpose then there will be bright future of its export in the international market also.

Nutrients present in 100gm Foxnut

Protein	9.7gm
Fats	0.1 gm
Carbohydrates	76.9gm
Fiber	14.5gm
Total lipid	0.1 gm
Calcium	60gm
Iron	1.4gm

Constraints In The Field Of Euryale Cultivation:

The demand of Euryale ferox (Foxnut) is increasing very rapidly in the Madhubani district but production is very low as compare to demand. As a result, production did not compete demand. The use of obsolete machinery and traditional method of farming is responsible for low production of Euryale ferox (Foxnut). Lots of programmes and projects are launched by the government in this field to increase the production of Euryale ferox like as- but they are also not giving proper result. The government organise training programmes for the farmers who are engaged in the Eurayle ferox with the

cooperation of various organisations like as ICAR, NGOs etc to solve the problem of cultivators but the information gap and lack of interest among Euryale ferox cultivators is the major constraint. Lack of scientific knowledge and skills in Euryale ferox cultivators is also the major cause of decreasing foxnut production in the Madhubani district because they did not know that how they will increase their production by the help of scientific method and good technical skills.

Polluted water bodies is the serious problem behind the decreasing production of Euryale ferox. Sometimes mismanagement of ponds

or other waterbodies and wetlands also ruined the ferox because of lack of proper knowledge of water bodies. The lack of storage facilities and supply chain is the big challenge for the Euryale ferox cultivators because the absence of these facilities are responsible for the spoiling of product. Madhubani is enrich in Euryale ferox cultivation but inspite of all these, government did not establish any Foxnut processing industry. Some industries are established at here on the basis of private ownership. Most of the work are done manually after the cultivation of raw foxnut from farmland because machines are very expensive and it is not easy for poor farmers to invest large amount in machine tools.

Diseases of Foxnut Crop and Their Prevention:

Foxnut cultivation is mostly affected from pests. The plant is carried out in deep water and farmers did not give more attention to crops due to this. As a result, they suffer heavy loss in the end. Diseases are mainly occurs in the plant, leaves and stem of the Foxnut crop. Rotting disease is very common in the Foxnut plant as it is caused by the Fungi like as – *Fusarium*, *Pithium* and *Rhizoctonia*. If infected seed germinate then its root start rotting. As a result, plant did not survive and after sometimes it die. Sometimes it is very difficult to find out the infected plants because they looks healthy but after sometimes disease is identified from fruit because fruits of these infected plants are underdeveloped. Leaf spot disease is also very common in plants. Firstly, an irregular-shaped spot appear on the leaves, which gradually separated leaves from the plant and after sometimes plant become leafless and then die. Polluted water bodies is very harmful for the Foxnut crop and is responsible for various diseases. So, it is very necessary to keep pond clean to save the crop from diseases. Give fertilizers according to the suggestion of expert because maximum and minimum both quantity is not good for plant. Use pesticides under the guidance of expert because if we give without proper knowledge then it may be harmful for the crops.

Government Initiatives In Foxnut Cultivation:

At present, state government provide 50% subsidy to the Foxnut cultivators. Government decided to take 4% Vat on the selling of popped Foxnut or Makhana. NABARD which is the organisation of government of India also give 25% subsidy on the Foxnut cultivation to encourage farmers. The government is also giving subsidy in the purchasing of disel, seeds and other machine tools which is used by the farmers in the Foxnut or makhana farming to encourage cultivators. Government give Rs. 16000/- to cultivators for Pond and Field system.

good crops of Euryale
Present Situation Of Foxnut Cultivation In The Madhubani District:

The production of Foxnut (Euryale Ferox) or Makhana is decreasing very rapidly in few decades in Madhubani district and is increasing in the neighbouring districts like as Saharsha, Supaul, Purnea etc. The reason behind the decreasing production of Foxnut or Makhana is lack of scientific methods obsolete machinery, traditional method of farming etc in the Madhubani district. 'One District One Programme' was launched by the central government to increase the production and processing of raw Foxnut in which Madhubani district is also selected because of the favourable condition of Foxnut farming and good production of Foxnut but this programme I not giving proper result. Government and various other agencies organise training programmes for cultivators that how to harness water bodies according to Foxnut farming, reasons behind the decreasing production and how to overcome from it, pest problems, methods to solve various problems which farmers face during farming, how to increase production, scientific method of farming etc but farmers did not show proper interest towards production in the Madhubani district. Today also processing of raw matrial which is known as UR (*locally called Guri*) is done manually at maximum places in the Madhubani district which take long time in processing and skilled worker is necessary for this work but in the adjoining districts of Madhubani, this work is done by machines at maximum places. The reason behind the manual processing of raw product is highly expensive machine tools which are not affordable for most of the farmers who are engaged in this work. 'Makhana research institute' which is established by the ICAR as its regional center for the development of Foxnut. The center introduced new methods and technology related with the Foxnut farming and its processing. Today Foxnut farming is not limited to the water bodies only. Farmers start growing it in the agricultural lands also with paddy and wheat also but it is not started in the Madhubani which is the main reason behind the increasing production in other districts and decreasing production in the Madhubani. Polluted water bodies is a great challenge for the growers because it not only decrease the production of crop but also responsible for various infectious diseases in the Foxnut crop. Swarn Vaidehi, one of the important variety of Makhana developed by the ICAR is now very popular among Foxnut cultivators because its yield potential is about 3t/ha which is very high as compare to traditional variety.

Blocks with highest no. of ponds and watery area (in Ha)

Blocks	No. of ponds	Watery Area
Benipatti	500	200.10
Babubarhi	250	150.14
Andhrathadhi	230	120.18
Madhwapur	198	200.53
Jhanjharpur	200	190.18
Bisfi	170	150.53

Source: International Journal of Zoogy and Research,(2017) vol.7

Suggestive Measures:

Suggestive measures are very important for the flood-prone region like Madhubani because every year heavy loss of life, property is very common at here. Destruction of crops are very common due to flood. Farmers are also facing economic problem and don't have proper ideas of latest machines. Harnessing of water bodies is also very important in Foxnut cultivation. So, proper management is very necessary for this region to overcome these problem in few aspect. Some of them are given below :

1. Growing of traditional crops like Paddy and Wheat cause heavy destruction and heavy loss to the farmer in the flood-prone region. So, it is much better to grow those crops which can easily survive during flood also like as Foxnut.
2. Harnessing of water bodies is very important in the Foxnut cultivation because the growth of Foxnut plant is depend on it. So, water management is very important in the Foxnut cultivation.
3. Madhubani has favourable condition for Foxnut farming and it is the important crop of here but inspite of all these, its production is decreasing in few decades because of obsolete machine tools and traditional method of farming. If cultivators will use the newly machines and grow crops scientifically then production will increase definitely.
4. Farmers are facing financial problems also in purchasing machines tools and other related things of Foxnut cultivation because subsidy is less on these things and farmers don't have more ideas of these subsidy. So, it is very important to introduce these programmes to them for their benefits.
5. There is no loan and scheme for Foxnut cultivation. If crops are ruined then government did not give any financial help to the farmers which make them economically weak. No loan facility for Foxnut cultivation also create problem for the farmers. So, there should be programme and loan facilities for those farmers whose crops are ruined or they are economically weak.
6. The production of Foxnut is good in the Madhubani district but there is lack of Makhana

processing unit in the region. Few of them are established at here but they are running on the basis of private ownership like as- the processing unit of Andhrathadhi and Arer. If government will take interest on the establishment of Makhana processing plant then this region will become the manufacturing in the near future.

7. Polluted water bodies and pests both of them are harmful for the Foxnut crop. Proper care of crop is very necessary for the Foxnut crop to protect it from the disease otherwise it did not survive. Polluted water bodies decrease the crop production and also responsible for diseases in crops. So, conservation of water bodies and pest control under the guidance of scientists is very important to protect crop from destruction.
8. There is lack of storage facilities in the region. If production will increase then there is no any center to keep products safely which increase the chances of crop destruction. So, it is very to provide storage facilities to the farmers.

Conclusion :

As a coclusion, we can say that madhubani is an important district of bihar and the district has good position in foxnut farming. The region is flood prone and the destruction of crop is very common at here due to flood. So the focxnut farming is good option for those areas where crops are ruined due to flood and farmers start showing interest towards it but pollution of water bodies, climate conditions, primitive method of farming unskilled workers , obsolete machinery, no mpore ideas of government policies unability of storage facilities etc. government and some agencies are doing work in this field to overcome these problems but it didn't give proper result at present.

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